

DETERMINING THE FACT OF A BREAK IN THE NEUTRAL WIRE IN NETWORKS AND ASSESSING THE MAGNITUDE OF POSSIBLE OVERVOLTAGE BASED ON THE ANALYSIS OF CURRENT SIGNALS ONLY

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Abstract

The use of microprocessor technology in automatic circuit breakers for protecting electrical networks allows several different types of protection based solely on the analysis of system currents to be combined in the release mechanism. This paper proposes a method for determining the fact of a zero wire (neutral) break in a four-wire power supply system and calculating possible overvoltage at consumers, based solely on the analysis of load currents at two adjacent moments in time.

A formula is derived showing the equality of relative changes in phase currents during a neutral break, based on which the neutral zero offset voltage is determined and an estimate of the magnitude of phase overvoltage is given.

To increase the reliability of determining the fact of a neutral break using the method described above, an additional method is proposed, based on the summation discretes of simultaneously counted three phase currents, which allows the fact of a break to be determined directly at the moment of the incident.

An algorithm for constructing protection against overvoltage in the event of a neutral break is considered, which can be implemented in the circuit breakers of relay protection.

Keywords: Four-wire system, neutral wire break, neutral bias voltages, overvoltage.

Introduction

Currently, the main means of protecting electrical networks are circuit breakers, the main function of which is to protect networks from short circuits and overloads.

However, for four-wire networks, protection against overvoltage's that may occur when the neutral wire (neutral) is broken is also necessary. Such protection is carried out using a voltage relay, such as the RN-03-02 relay [1], which must be supplemented with an additional contactor to disconnect the three-phase load.

A break in the neutral wire in four-wire 0.4 kV networks can lead to a significant voltage imbalance in single-phase consumers (up to 1.73 times) and cause the failure of a number of household electrical receivers. Therefore, the task of determining the fact of a neutral break and protecting consumers from possible overvoltage in this case is relevant.

It would be advisable to supplement the circuit breaker tripping devices with a function of protection against overvoltage, when the neutral is broken. But, since the operation of the latest's, both for analysis and for operational power supply, uses only signals from current sensors, then the additional function - protection against neutral breakage should be based only on the analysis of the phase current system.

There are known works on determining the fact of breakage of the neutral wire, based only on information about the phase current system [2].

In work [2], an original method of replacing the real asymmetric current system with one equalized by modules, but with phase angles of the real system currents is used. In this case, an artificial signal of the total three-phase power is formed and the variable component of this signal is analyzed before and after the breakage, based on the value of which both the fact of breakage and the level of possible overvoltage's in the system are determined.

However, this method is limited by the condition of proximity or even equality of the phase power factors. If the difference in the values of $\cos\varphi$ of the phase loads is more than 11%, the level of the variable component before the break will exceed its level corresponding to the permissible overvoltage in the network and a false tripping of the protection will occur.

In this paper, an attempt is made to generally determine the fact of a neutral break in networks with uneven phase loading, based only on the analysis of the change in the current system during a break, to determine the change in the neutral bias voltage and to identify dangerous overvoltage in consumers.

Justification of the method

Figure 1 shows a simplified diagram of a network consisting of one group of electrical receivers. A neutral break can occur at point K of the line.

Fig.1 Calculation scheme of the power supply network

With an asymmetrical phase load between the neutral of the voltage source and the neutral of the receivers, a zero bias voltage arises, equal to (see Theoretical foundations of electrical engineering):

$$\dot{U}_0 = \frac{\dot{E}_A \dot{Y}_A + \dot{E}_B \dot{Y}_B + \dot{E}_C \dot{Y}_C}{\dot{Y}_A + \dot{Y}_B + \dot{Y}_C + \dot{Y}_0}, \quad (1)$$

where $\dot{E}_{A,B,C}$ - are the phase EMF complexes, $\dot{Y}_{A,B,C}$ and \dot{Y}_0 - are the load conductivity complexes and the neutral conductivity complex.

The phase currents are found from the expressions:

$$I_A = (\dot{E}_A - \dot{U}_0) \dot{Y}_A, I_B = (\dot{E}_B - \dot{U}_0) \dot{Y}_B, I_C = (\dot{E}_C - \dot{U}_0) \dot{Y}_C. \quad (2)$$

If the neutral wire is broken, $\dot{Y}_0 = 0$ and the neutral offset can increase significantly and will be equal to:

$$\dot{U}_{00} = \frac{\dot{E}_A \dot{Y}_A + \dot{E}_B \dot{Y}_B + \dot{E}_C \dot{Y}_C}{\dot{Y}_A + \dot{Y}_B + \dot{Y}_C}, \quad (3)$$

accordingly, in formulas (2) for currents, the value \dot{U}_0 should be replaced by \dot{U}_{00} .

In further analysis, we will make two assumptions:

Because conductivity of the neutral wire is significantly greater than the sum of the load conductivities, then the value of the neutral bias \dot{U}_0 according to (1) will be close to zero and can be neglected compared to the phase EMF.

We will also neglect the internal resistance of the voltage source, and include the resistances of the phase wires in the load resistances. With this assumption, the voltages on the consumer buses will be equal to the EMF of the power sources.

When the neutral wire breaks with an uneven load, the neutral bias voltage can increase significantly, and our task is precisely to determine and evaluate this value.

We will determine the increments of the currents of the group of receivers when the neutral is broken:

$$\Delta I_i = (\dot{E}_i - \dot{U}_{00}) \dot{Y}_i - (\dot{E}_i - \dot{U}_0) \dot{Y}_i = -(\dot{U}_{00} - \dot{U}_0) \dot{Y}_i, \quad (4)$$

here index "i" corresponds to indexes A, B, C of the phases of electrical receivers.

The relative value of change in load currents will be equal to:

$$\delta_i = \frac{\Delta I_i}{I_i} = -\frac{\dot{U}_{00} - \dot{U}_0}{\dot{E}_i - \dot{U}_0}, \quad (5)$$

The magnitude of the neutral displacement U_0 in normal mode is quite small, compared to the phase voltages E_i , and can be neglected in the denominator (5). In some cases, with a large asymmetry of loads, it can also be neglected in the numerator (5), but we will retain it in the approximate formula

$$\delta_i = \frac{\Delta I_i}{I_i} \approx -\frac{\dot{U}_{00} - \dot{U}_0}{\dot{E}_i}, \quad (6)$$

Formula (6) shows that the values of δ_i are the same in absolute value for all phases, and differ only in phase angles of supply voltages (EMF). That is, we can conclude that when the neutral is broken, the complexes of relative changes in phase currents are approximately equal to the ratio of the change in the difference in neutral bias voltages after and before the break, to the corresponding phase EMF, and the moduli of these ratios are equal to each other. Thus, the criterion for a neutral break is a simultaneous change in three phase currents by relative values equal in absolute value. That is, when scanning phase currents, it is necessary to calculate the complexes of their differences in adjacent intervals and compare the moduli of the ratio of these differences to the currents of the previous interval. Detection of equality of three modules of ratios indicates the fact of a neutral break in the network in the current interval.

Note: the value of the current difference ΔI_i must be calculated as the difference in the complexes of currents of the current and previous intervals, and not as the difference in their modules.

When establishing the fact of a neutral break, from any of the three equalities (6) it is possible to determine the module of the difference in neutral bias voltages

$$|\dot{U}_{00} - \dot{U}_0| = E_A \cdot \Delta I_i / I_i, \quad (7)$$

Unfortunately, the obtained value of the neutral bias voltage difference modulus does not allow us to accurately determine the values of phase voltages after the break, since the actual value and argument of the neutral bias voltage \dot{U}_{00} are unknown. But even if the value of \dot{U}_0 could be neglected, the obtained value of \dot{U}_{00} would still not allow us to determine the true values of phase voltages. This is due to the fact that the phase angles in the above formulas (1) - (6) are measured from the zero phase of the phase A voltage. But when using only current signals, it is possible to accurately determine the phase angles of the currents in relation to the base current, for example, to the current of phase A before the break, but then the phase of the zero bias

voltage \dot{U}_{00} will differ from the true phase by the system angle φ_A of the phase A current shift relative to the voltage of this phase.

If the load power factor $\cos\varphi_A$ of the base phase A is approximately known in advance and the value of \dot{U}_0 can be neglected, then the phase voltages on the loads of the emergency section can be approximately determined

$$U_i \approx |\dot{E}_i - \dot{U}_{00}e^{-j\varphi_A}| \quad (8)$$

However, knowing the difference in the neutral bias voltage modules, it is possible to estimate possible overvoltage. The maximum increase in voltage of one of the phases will occur when the real phase of the neutral bias voltage \dot{U}_{00} is equal to 180° with respect to the phase voltage of one of the phases. Therefore, it is possible to estimate the maximum value of the voltage module \dot{U}_{00} , which can lead to an unacceptable overvoltage on the load of one of the phases. Moreover, the fact that we calculate the difference module $|\dot{U}_{00} - \dot{U}_0|$ gives us some reserve, since if this difference exceeds the permissible value, then \dot{U}_{00} even more exceeds the permissible value. Thus, if the permissible value of the phase overvoltage is 20%, then, with some reserve, the relative value \dot{U}_{00}/E can be taken equal to 20%.

The advantage of the proposed method is that if the neutral break is confirmed, it allows for a fairly accurate assessment of possible overvoltage in the network, based only on information about phase currents.

Let us consider some limitations of the method under consideration

First of all, let us touch upon the terms "interval" and "adjacent interval". All the above analytical calculations were carried out for steady-state modes in the network both before and after the neutral break. When the neutral breaks in an essentially inductive network, a transient process will occur, this will fade over several periods. Therefore, even if the current period in the network corresponds to a steady-state process, the period following it cannot be considered a subsequent interval, since even if a neutral break occurred during this period, the steady-state process will occur after 3-4 periods of network voltage. Therefore, the calculation of the current difference $\Delta\dot{I}_i$ can be carried out not every period, but at intervals of 3-4 periods. The only condition for the interval where the equality of relative current increments will be revealed is the constancy of the load conductivity before and after the break.

It should be noted, however, that there is some uncertainty in establishing the fact of a neutral break when using the proposed method. It would be desirable for the fact of a break to be determined immediately during the current period of the break.

It turns out that this is possible if one assumption is fulfilled, the probability of which is very high. Let us assume that the load of a four-wire system is always asymmetrical. Then, in normal mode, when scanning a system of three phase currents, the algebraic sum of simultaneously counted discretely will always be non-

zero.

On the contrary, when a neutral breaks, according to Kirchhoff's 1st law, the sum of three simultaneously taken discretely will be zero, regardless of the presence of a transient process and the presence of higher harmonics in the network. This will be the exact criterion for a neutral break in the network directly at the time of the incident. Then, having identified the fact of a break in the current period and having waited 3-4 periods, it is possible to calculate the complexes of the phase current differences and use the considered relationships of the above-described method, based on the equality of the relative values of the change in phase currents when the neutral is broken.

To summarize the above, we can consider the algorithm of the proposed method.

1. Scan the currents of three phases and calculate the algebraic sum of three discrete phase currents at each cycle. If it turns out that the sum of the discretely is not equal to zero, then calculate and store the complexes and moduli of the currents in this period.

2. If it turns out that the sum of the discretely is equal to zero at several bars of the current period (more precisely, does not exceed one ADC sampling quantum), then draw a conclusion about a neutral break in this period. Take the previous period as the previous interval.

3. We skip 3-4 scanning cycles. Take the first period after the delay as the subsequent interval and calculate the complexes and moduli of the currents in this period.

4. Determine the complexes of current increments for each phase at the specified intervals.

5. Determine 3 modules δi of the ratio of the change in phase currents of the current interval to the currents of the previous interval and compare them with each other. The equality (or rather proximity) of these three ratios is an additional confirmation of the fact of neutral breakage. Calculate the average value δ_{mid} of these ratios.

5. Using formula (6), determine the absolute value of the neutral bias voltage difference. $|\dot{U}_{00} - \dot{U}_0| = E_A \cdot \delta_{mid}$. If this value exceeds the permissible overvoltage value, an emergency signal is generated to the circuit breaker trip unit to disconnect the line.

Table 1 shows the results of calculating the relative difference in neutral bias voltages, when it breaks, for two phase load distribution ratios (*min-max-min* and *max-min-max*) with an equal nonlinearity coefficient $K_Y = \frac{Y_{\max}}{Y_{\min}} = 2$, taking into account different levels of losses in the network.

Comparison of the calculated value of δ_{cp} with the exact value shows that the error does not exceed 1.5%, which allows us to estimate the magnitude of possible overvoltage quite accurately. In the two examples presented, the overvoltage level exceeds or is close to the permissible value.

Table 1.

Phase loads	Network Losses %	δ_A	δ_B	δ_C	δ_{mid}	Exact value $ \dot{U}_{00} - \dot{U}_0 /E_A$	Error %
0.5 -1- 0.5	2	0.237	0.242	0.241	0.24	0.238	0.84
	3	0.23	0.238	0.236	0.235	0.233	0.86
	5	0.218	0.231	0.227	0.225	0.222	1.35
1- 0.5 -1	0	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0
	2	0.189	0.189	0.193	0.19	0.189	0.529
	3	0.184	0.183	0.189	0.186	0.184	1.086
	5	0.175	0.172	0.182	0.176	0.174	1.15

Conclusion

The paper analyzes the change in the current system in a four-wire power supply system when the neutral is broken. A formula is derived showing that the complexes of relative changes in phase currents when the neutral is broken are equal to the relative changes in the neutral bias voltages. In this case, the moduli of the phase current change ratios are approximately equal. On this basis, a criterion for determining the fact of a neutral break is formulated: evidence of a neutral break is a simultaneous change in three phase currents by equal relative values.

The established approximate equality of the moduli of the phase current ratios made it possible to determine the change in the neutral bias voltages of the system as the product of their average value and the phase voltage value. This allowed us to estimate the possible level of overvoltage in the system during a break.

An additional method is proposed that allows increasing the reliability of determining the fact of a neutral break the method is based on the analysis of the sum

of simultaneously calculated discrete three phase currents, which allows us to determine the fact of a break directly at the moment of the incident.

The paper compares the results obtained on the basis of the proposed method with an accurate analytical calculation for two cases of uneven load at different levels of losses in the network, and shows the high accuracy of the proposed method.

An algorithm for the proposed method is formulated, allowing it to be integrated into the microprocessor system of circuit.

References

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